

Screening, Brief Interventions, and Referral to Treatment in the ED

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Background

Substance Use Disorders (SUD)

- Alcohol Use Disorder is most prevalent
- Declared public health crisis in 2016
- US \$400B/yr.
- Orange County \$269M; 11,000 hospitalizations 2011 & 2012
- Alcohol deaths 88,000 US 2006-2010

Purpose

- To implement and evaluate the SBIRT intervention in the Emergency Care Center (ECC) at St. Joseph Hospital-Orange (SJO)

SBIRT

- **S:** Screening for substance use
- **BI:** Brief motivational intervention (MI) for those with a positive screen
- **RT:** Referral to appropriate treatment

Participants' Demographics

Theoretical Framework: Ottawa Model of Research Use, 2004

Methods & Implementation

- **Design:** Translation of evidence into practice.
- **Settings:** SJO, 53 ECC beds, ~7000 patients/monthly.
- **Sample:** RN (N=125).
- **Measures:** C-Scale (SBIRT) knowledge & confidence; percentage of SBIRT performance
- **Procedures:**
 - Two 4-hour SBIRT train-the-trainers classes for superusers
 - Six 1.5-hour training classes for registered nurses
 - Integration of SBIRT into the ECC nursing workflow.
 - Training, SBIRT c-scale baseline, post, 6-12 weeks follow up

Results

SBIRT Performance

- 3.5% (228/6510) eligible patients received pre-screening.
- Six patient received screening for drug use and eleven for alcohol use.

C-scale Results

Lessons Learned

- Significant increase in knowledge of SBIRT, but did not translate to practice.
- Practice change is a challenging, slow process

Challenges

- Pre-screening reassignment created confusion.
- Lack of constant face-to-face interaction between staff and project leader.
- Inability to incorporate all SBIRT screening tools in EHR
- Low rate of C-scale return at 6 and 12 weeks

Conclusion

- Training RNs and incorporation of SBIRT in the workflow is feasible, but achieving practice change is a complex process.

Recommendations

- Institute more frequent SBIRT reminders.
- Train more SBIRT superusers.
- Incorporate all SBIRT screening tools in EHR and create a user-friendly template.
- Longer follow-up periods to evaluate sustainability and performance.
- Further research on SBIRT efficacy on patients' substance use behaviors

References

